

ESTABLISHMENT OF POW CAMPS IN TURKESTAN DURING THE FIRST WORLD WAR

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According to various sources, about 2.5 million officers and soldiers, mainly citizens of Austria-Hungary and Germany, were captured in the territory of the Russian Empire during the First World War. Already in the first month of the war, places intended for the permanent accommodation of prisoners of war were prepared within the Moscow, Kazan, Omsk and Irkutsk military districts, and the military camps in these areas soon began to fill up. In this regard, the General Directorate of the General Staff began to think about preparing new places for the arrival of large parties of prisoners of war in the future.

During World War I, many Austro-Hungarian and German soldiers were captured by the Soviet soldiers. Statistics show that there were 2.5 million Austro-Hungarian and 200,000 German prisoners of war during and after World War I. Thousands of Austrian soldiers became prisoners during 1914 [9].

From the beginning of the First World War to December 1917, Russia captured the soldiers of the Entente. By 1917, it had the second largest number of prisoners of war among those participating in the war. 2.4 million of the more than 5 million soldiers captured throughout Russia were captured [4].

More than 2 million prisoners of war in Russia - 90 percent of those captured were Austro-Hungarian soldiers. The Austro-Hungarian Empire was a multinational state. Slavs (Poles, Romanians, Czechs, Slovaks, Serbs, Croats, Slovenes) made up half of the Austro-Hungarians in captivity, Germans and Hungarians made up $\frac{1}{4}$, and Italians and Romanians made up the rest. The second largest group of prisoners of war were members of the German army. About 168,000 German soldiers were captured.

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The number of prisoners of Ottoman Turks and Bulgarians was estimated to be about 50,000 [3].

In 1914, the Austro-Hungarians, Germans, Slavs, and Romanians who were captured in Russia by the order of the General Staff were placed in the Urals, Siberia, Turkestan and the Far East [1]. During World War I, more than 400 military camps were established on the territory of Russia [2]. Russia planned to settle prisoners of war only in remote areas far from the main cities. They were mainly sent to the regions reached by railway lines. Therefore, they knew that railway transport would be of great help in placing prisoners of war in military camps. But suddenly there were changes in the plans of the Russians regarding the placement of prisoners. This, in turn, was connected with the increase of prisoners of war on the territory of Russia.

Initially, the prisoners of war were placed in military camps in Kiev, Penza, Kazan and Turkestan, and then they were dispersed to different regions according to their ethnic origin. The Slavs were sent to an area near the border with Kazakhstan, not far from Omsk in south-central Russia. Hungarians and Germans became prisoners of war in Siberian camps. The location of the camps also played an important role in the difficult lifestyle of political military prisoners. For example, in Murmansk, in the far north-west of Russia, the conditions of the soldiers who were forced to work as prisoners of war were much worse than those in the southern parts of the empire.

According to the plan, the territory of Turkestan was not predetermined for prisoners of war, but, as noted above, the increase in the number of prisoners led to their placement in the territory of Turkestan. In the telegram No. 6158 of the Chief of the General Staff to the Chief of the General Staff of the Turkestan District on August 30, 1914, it was announced that Turkestan was designated as a place for permanent placement of prisoners of war [6]. First, in September 1914, the flow of prisoners of war was directed to the city military camps of Turkestan. Prisoners of war of the Austro-Hungarian and German armies began to arrive in Tashkent.

First, it was planned to accommodate about 10,000 prisoners of war in Turkestan. But by the end of 1914, the number of prisoners of war that was planned to

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be placed in Turkestan became too large. As of July 21, 1915, there were about 150,000 prisoners of war in the Turkestan military district.

After the start of hostilities, more than 50,000 prisoners of war belonging to different nationalities were placed in the territory of Turkestan. Most of them were sent to the Tashkent region. At first, it was not difficult to place them in military camps. Barracks under the jurisdiction of the Turkestan Military District (TurkVO) were given to the prisoners. Sometimes prisoners of war were forced to move from one camp to another. For example, a prisoner of war named Ferdinand Effenberg was brought to Peremyshl on March 22, 1915, then with other prisoners of war he was sent first to Kiev, then to Moscow, in April to Tashkent, in July to Samarkand and finally to Siberia [7].

By June 1915, the number of prisoners of war in the Turkestan region exceeded 148,000. They were placed in 37 specially built military camps, barracks and other places at the disposal of the Turkestan military district[5]. The camps in the territories belonging to the Turkestan military district began to run out of places to house prisoners of war. Because the number of prisoners of war was increasing day by day. For example, the special areas allocated for the POW camp in Kattakorgon were intended to accommodate only 600 prisoners of war, but in practice it was twice as many, i.e. 1200 people. In Samarkand, these numbers showed 1,000 people instead of 500. Under these conditions, to solve this problem, bunk beds were brought and installed in military camps. This event was the only way to accommodate the capacity of prisoners mentioned above. 600 prisoners of war who were to be placed in the camp in Chorjoi were sent to the barges of the Amudarya flotilla [4]. In the Syrdarya region, the building of the higher educational institution in Kazalinsk was given to 100 prisoners of war officers. The above cases were also noted in Perovsk.

According to Sterling, the head of the American mission, in 1915 there were 82,425 Austro-Hungarian and 3,812 German prisoners of war in Turkestan [8]. By March 1916, the number of prisoners of war in the country reached 200,000. Their number has increased even more than the population of the cities where they settled.

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Even the government of Turkestan was worried about the areas where these prisoners of war were placed, because in case of various disturbances, of course, the prisoners of war and representatives of the local population together would form a great force.

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